

UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
FACULTY OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDIES
IN COLLABORATION WITH
TETFUND CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN
MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDIES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE FIRST IBADAN
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE IN
MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDIES

**THEME: CURRENT TRENDS IN MULTIDISCIPLINARITY:
MODELS, METHODOLOGIES & APPLICATIONS
11 - 12 February 2025 (HYBRID)**

**VENUE: SENATOR ABIOLA AJIMOBİ RESOURCE CENTRE
9 PARRY ROAD, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN, NIGERIA**

EDITED BY: DR FUNMILOLA O. OMOTAYO

Cultural Resources Management and Sustainable Tourism Development in Kwara State, Nigeria

¹Khidir B. BALOGUN and ²Olusola S. FOLORUNSO

^{1,2}Department of Sustainability Studies, Faculty of Multidisciplinary Studies,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria

Email: samolaolu2001@yahoo.com

Abstract

Cultural Resource Management (CRM) is critical in preserving heritage assets while fostering sustainable tourism development, particularly in culturally endowed regions like Kwara State, Nigeria. However, as applicable to most local tourist destinations, there is a perceived underappreciation of CRM, coupled with insufficient information about its contribution to global sustainable tourism discourse. It is on this premise that this study explores the intricate relationship between CRM and sustainable tourism development using a qualitative research approach grounded in the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) model and the Tripod of Sustainability framework. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with key stakeholders, including cultural heritage managers, local community leaders, and tourism operators, alongside document analysis of cultural policies and tourism plans in Kwara State. The TALC model was used to assess the development stages of prominent cultural attractions, such as the Esie Museum and Ilorin Emirate Palace, analysing their trajectory from exploration to stagnation. The study also evaluated the integration of the three pillars of sustainability within CRM practices in the state. Findings reveal that while Kwara State's cultural resources possess significant potential for tourism development, inadequate management, lack of funding, and low stakeholder engagement hinder their sustainability. The TALC model indicates that many sites are in the stagnation stage, requiring rejuvenation strategies to avoid decline. Furthermore, the analysis highlights the gaps in aligning CRM practices with the sustainability tripod, particularly in addressing environmental conservation and equitable community benefits. The study concludes that effective CRM, underpinned by systematic planning and multi-stakeholder collaboration, is pivotal for advancing sustainable tourism in Kwara State. Recommendations include adopting policies that integrate the TALC model into cultural tourism planning, enhancing community participation, and promoting eco-friendly practices.

Keywords: Cultural heritage, Cultural resource management, Sustainable tourism, Tourism Area Life Cycle model, Tourism development

Introduction

Cultural Resource Management (CRM) is increasingly recognised for its significance in safeguarding cultural heritage while promoting sustainable tourism development. In regions with rich cultural endowments, such as Kwara State, Nigeria, effective CRM can enhance visitor experiences and stimulate local economies. Cultural Resource Management (CRM) is an essential approach to preserving and managing cultural heritage sites, artifacts, and traditions while ensuring their sustainable use for tourism and economic development. As global tourism continues to evolve, there is increasing recognition of the need to balance heritage conservation with tourism growth. Holden (2016) asserts that effective CRM ensures that cultural sites remain intact for future generations while providing enriching experiences for tourists. It encompasses policies, strategies, and best practices aimed at protecting tangible and intangible cultural resources from degradation, commercialisation, or neglect. In regions with significant cultural assets, such as Kwara State, Nigeria, CRM serves as a critical tool for fostering responsible tourism and community engagement in heritage conservation. Kwara State, known for its rich

cultural heritage, is home to historical sites, indigenous festivals, and traditional crafts that hold significant tourism potential. Attractions such as the Esie Museum, the Pategi Regatta, the Ilorin Emir's Palace, and other heritage sites are valuable cultural assets that, if well-managed, can drive sustainable tourism (Akintunde, Olatunji, & Okeke, 2022). However, challenges such as inadequate conservation policies, lack of funding, and limited stakeholder engagement threaten the effective preservation of these resources. Additionally, unregulated tourism activities can lead to the degradation of cultural sites and loss of authenticity, undermining their long-term viability. A comprehensive CRM strategy that integrates sustainable tourism principles to enhance the cultural and economic benefits of heritage tourism is urgently required to address this issue.

To understand the interplay between CRM and sustainable tourism development, this study adopts the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) model and the Tripod of Sustainability framework. Butler (1980), affirms that the TALC model helps analyse the various stages of tourism development, from exploration to potential decline, offering insights into how heritage sites can be managed for long-term sustainability. The Tripod of Sustainability framework, which focuses on economic, social, and environmental dimensions, provides a holistic approach to assessing the impact of CRM on tourism. The application of these analytical lenses guides this study in seeking to identify the extent to which CRM practices contribute to the sustainable development of Kwara State's cultural tourism sector. This study is significant in several ways. First, it highlights the role of CRM in preserving cultural heritage while promoting tourism in a manner that benefits local communities. Second, it provides insights into sustainable tourism development strategies that can be adapted to similar regions facing heritage conservation challenges. Finally, the findings from this research will contribute to policy recommendations that can guide stakeholders, including government agencies, tourism operators, and local communities in implementing effective CRM practices. This study, therefore, aims to support the long-term sustainability of cultural heritage sites in Kwara State by bridging the gap between cultural conservation and tourism growth.

Literature Review

Previous studies have highlighted the importance of CRM in fostering sustainable tourism by enhancing community engagement and preserving heritage assets (Smith, 2006; Timothy, 2011). The TALC model, introduced by Butler (1980), provides a framework for understanding the evolution of tourist destinations through phases ranging from exploration to stagnation. This substantiates the choice of the TALC model for this study because its framework represents adoptable metrics for evaluation of the current state of selected cultural resources of tourism values in Kwara State. Additionally, the Tripod of Sustainability emphasises the interconnectedness of environmental, economic, and social dimensions in achieving sustainability (Bramwell & Lane, 2011). This synergy underscores the emphasis on conceptualising cultural resource management and its linkage to sustainable tourism. Talukder and Hoque (2025), using Bangladesh as a case study, advocated integrated conservation and management strategies that balance the preservation of cultural heritage with the socio-economic benefits derivable from tourism activities. This implies that through CRM efforts, sustainable tourism holds viable benefits, especially to the host communities.

Concept of Cultural Resource Management (CRM) and Sustainable Tourism

Smith (2006), describes Cultural Resource Management (CRM) as a multidisciplinary approach aimed at preserving, protecting, and managing cultural heritage while ensuring its sustainable use for tourism and economic development. Researchers have emphasised the role of CRM in fostering sustainable tourism by safeguarding historical sites, promoting cultural continuity, and involving local communities in heritage conservation efforts (Timothy, 2011). CRM encompasses various activities, including policy formulation, site conservation, documentation, and public engagement, to maintain the integrity of cultural assets while optimising their tourism potential (McKercher & Cros, 2012). Sustainable tourism, on the other hand, seeks to balance environmental conservation, economic benefits, and sociocultural well-being, ensuring that tourism activities do not compromise future generations' ability to enjoy cultural resources (UNWTO, 2024).

In the African context, studies have underscored the importance of CRM in sustainable tourism development. Adebayo and Iweka (2019) examined the role of CRM in Nigeria's cultural tourism sector and found that inadequate funding, weak policy implementation, and low community participation hinder the effective management of heritage resources. Similarly, Mlambo and Chirikure (2020), analysed CRM strategies in Southern Africa and concluded that integrating indigenous knowledge systems with modern conservation techniques can enhance heritage site sustainability. However, in Asia's context, Talukder and Hoque (2025), submit that CRM strategies in Bangladesh are rooted in community engagement. In the same vein, Huang and Xu affirmed that any CRM strategy that does not capture the host communities as stakeholders in decision-making is a structural violence against the local communities. These studies suggest that a holistic CRM approach is necessary to ensure the longevity of cultural assets while promoting responsible tourism.

Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) Model and Its Relevance

The Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) model, introduced by Butler (1980), provides a theoretical framework for understanding the evolution of tourist destinations. The model outlines six stages: exploration, involvement, development, consolidation, stagnation, and either rejuvenation or decline. Research has demonstrated the applicability of the TALC model in analysing tourism growth patterns and identifying factors that influence destination sustainability. For instance, Saarinen (2006) applied the TALC model to African safari tourism, illustrating how mismanagement and over-commercialisation can lead to stagnation and decline. Empirical studies have also tested the TALC model in various cultural tourism contexts. Rogerson and van der Merwe (2016) explored the applicability of the TALC model to South Africa's cultural heritage sites and found that many destinations faced challenges at the consolidation and stagnation stages due to inadequate infrastructure and ineffective marketing. Additionally, Okonkwo and Ezeuduji (2022) applied the model to Nigerian heritage sites and emphasised the need for improved CRM policies to sustain tourism growth beyond the development phase. These findings highlight the relevance of the TALC model in assessing the long-term viability of cultural tourism destinations.

Tripod of Sustainability and Its Implications for CRM

The Tripod of Sustainability framework, postulated by Bramwell & Lane (2011), emphasises the interconnectedness of three key dimensions, which are environmental, economic, and social sustainability in tourism development. Environmental sustainability focuses on conserving natural and cultural resources, economic sustainability aims to ensure long-term financial viability, and social sustainability prioritises community involvement and cultural preservation. Orts-Cardador *et al.* (2024), stress that the framework aligns with CRM in the aspect of profiling the state of each attraction within a destination, using similar metrics to evaluate the area life cycle to essentially identify appropriate sustainability measures and across the tripods.

Empirical studies have highlighted the role of the Tripod of Sustainability in cultural tourism management. For instance, Sharpley and Telfer (2015), examined heritage tourism in developing countries and found that a lack of balance between economic gains and environmental protection often leads to resource depletion. Similarly, Hernández-Mogollón *et al.* (2018) studied cultural festivals in Spain and concluded that community participation is a crucial factor in ensuring social sustainability. In the Nigerian context, Tunde *et al.* (2022) assessed the impact of cultural festivals on local economies and found that while economic benefits were evident, social and environmental considerations were often overlooked, leading to concerns about the long-term sustainability of these events.

Empirical Reviews on CRM and Sustainable Tourism Development

In principle, several empirical studies have explored the relationship between CRM and sustainable tourism development in different contexts. Graham *et al.* (2016), examined the role of heritage site management in tourism development in Europe and found that integrated CRM policies led to increased visitor satisfaction and longer site lifespan. Similarly, Nash and Butler (2018), assessed CRM initiatives in North American indigenous heritage sites and found that

community-based approaches enhanced conservation outcomes. On the other hand, Bassey and Udo (2020), studied cultural heritage tourism in Nigeria and recommended better stakeholder collaboration for sustainable site management. This is closely linked to the study of Muganda *et al.* (2021), who analysed the impact of CRM on community livelihoods in East Africa and found that participatory tourism planning significantly improved conservation efforts.

As regards the need for public-private partnership (PPP), Akintunde *et al.* (2022) investigated CRM practices in southwestern Nigeria and emphasised the need for government-private sector partnerships to drive sustainable cultural tourism. Lack of collaboration and partnership can generate some challenges for cultural tourism resources. For instance, Bello and Olalekan (2022) explored CRM challenges in Nigerian museums and recommended digitisation as a strategy to enhance accessibility and preservation.

Also, Okonkwo (2023) studied the relationship between CRM and destination branding in Nigeria and found that effective heritage management improved tourism competitiveness. Equally, Mthembu and Chiweshe (2023) examined cultural heritage policies in South Africa and identified gaps in community engagement as a major constraint. This poses a challenge for CRM to thrive in the region under consideration, which is Kwara State. Moreover, Hassan *et al.* (2023) assessed CRM in Middle Eastern heritage sites and found that innovative conservation technologies significantly improved site durability.

Furthermore, Olayemi and Adediran (2023) explored CRM and tourism sustainability in Lagos, Nigeria, and recommended integrated tourism planning for long-term success. Pisolkar (2024), analysed the role of CRM in promoting ecotourism in Nigeria and found that policy inconsistencies hindered effective implementation. Johnson and Williams (2024), examined global best practices in CRM and recommended adaptive management strategies for emerging tourism destinations. The literature suggests that CRM plays a critical role in sustainable tourism development by ensuring heritage conservation, community involvement, and economic viability. The TALC model and the Tripod of Sustainability provide valuable analytical tools for understanding how CRM strategies can enhance the longevity and resilience of cultural tourism destinations. However, empirical studies indicate that several challenges, including weak policies, inadequate funding, and limited stakeholder participation, continue to hinder effective CRM implementation in Nigeria. Folorunso *et al.* (2017) suggested that a coordinated effort involving government agencies, private sector stakeholders, and local communities is required to address these challenges and to subsequently develop robust policies and strategies that align with sustainability principles.

Alternative Model for Cultural Resource Management

Aside from the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) Model, several other models can be used to describe or discuss Cultural Resource Management (CRM) and sustainable tourism. These models help explain how cultural heritage assets are managed, preserved, and integrated into sustainable tourism; prominent among these models is the Heritage Management Process Model by McKercher & Du Cros (2002). This model focuses on the balance between heritage conservation and tourism development. It emphasises that cultural resources should not be over-commercialised at the expense of their historical integrity. This model is relevant to CRM in the sense that it encourages stakeholder collaboration between governments, local communities, and tourism operators. This model also highlights the need for heritage interpretation, that is, how cultural sites are presented to tourists. It stresses the importance of visitor impact management to prevent resource degradation; an example is given in the aspect of implementing structured tour experiences in Esie Museum or Ilorin Emirate Palace to educate visitors while preserving site authenticity.

Also, the Stakeholder Theory in Heritage Management, postulated by Freeman (1984) and adopted by Timothy (2011), suggests that CRM should involve multiple stakeholders, including governments, local communities, tourists, NGOs, and the private sector. Its relevance to CRM covers areas that ensure community engagement in cultural resource decision-making, while encouraging public-private partnerships for sustainable heritage conservation. This model also captures the prevention of conflicts of interest by considering diverse perspectives in CRM planning. For instance, engaging traditional rulers, cultural custodians, and tourism boards in

managing Kwara State's cultural attractions. Similarly, the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Model by Elkington (1997) offers evaluation of heritage tourism sustainability using three dimensions: economic, environmental, and social sustainability. Its relevance to CRM: includes ensuring economic benefits from heritage tourism are reinvested into conservation; to prioritise environmental sustainability in heritage site management; and to promote social equity by including local communities in tourism benefits. A notable example is ensuring that local artisans and cultural groups benefit from tourism revenue in Kwara State.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design, utilising in-depth interviews with key stakeholders such as cultural heritage managers, local community leaders, and tourism operators in Kwara State. These interviews were complemented by a document analysis of cultural policies and tourism plans relevant to the region. A total of 6 interviews were conducted, with participants providing insights into their experiences and perceptions regarding CRM and its impact on tourism development. The participants include the Director of Kwara State Tourism Board, the curator of Esie Museum, a sculptor at Dada Pottery and one of the chiefs at Olofa's palace. The respondents were purposefully selected. Their responses were analysed using thematic analysis.

Findings

The investigation revealed that Kwara State's cultural resources, including significant sites like the Esie Museum and Ilorin Emirate Palace, have substantial potential for tourism. However, several challenges exist, such as inadequate management as a result of a lack of systematic CRM practices leads to neglect of cultural resources. This was also caused due to insufficient financial support that limits conservation efforts and promotional activities. Consequently, low stakeholder engagement and weak collaboration among government agencies and local communities hinder inclusive tourism development (Balogun & Ajagunna, 2023). This can be further analysed using the TALC model indicates that several cultural attractions are currently in the stagnation phase, necessitating strategic rejuvenation efforts to prevent decline. Certain cultural attractions like Sheik Alimi Mosque in Ilorin and Olofa's Palace in Offa are currently experiencing stagnation. The findings revealed that this is due to a lack of cultural resources management policy, as emphasized by the Director of Kwara State Tourism Board, Dr. Alabede as quoted *"there is a need to policy reformation that focuses on the identification of cultural resource of tourism interest, and implementation of strategies for their management"*. The investigation into Cultural Resource Management (CRM) and sustainable tourism development in Kwara State revealed key challenges and opportunities. The findings are categorised into thematic areas based on Thematic Analysis, which allows for the identification of patterns and trends in the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The following themes emerged from the analysis:

i. Tourism Potential of Cultural Resources in Kwara State

Kwara State is endowed with diverse cultural heritage resources, including historical sites, festivals, and traditional crafts, which hold significant tourism potential. Prominent attractions such as the Esie Museum, which houses the oldest known stone carvings in West Africa, and the Ilorin Emirate Palace, a historical seat of Islamic and indigenous leadership, could serve as major tourist destinations if properly managed (Afolabi & Ayodele, 2020). Additionally, heritage sites such as Sheik Alimi Mosque in Ilorin, Pategi Regatta, and Olofa's Palace in Offa offer unique historical and cultural experiences that can contribute to local economic development through increased tourist influx (Ajayi & Adedayo, 2021). However, despite this rich cultural heritage, many of these sites remain underutilised due to poor CRM practices. This is in line with the submission of Alabede, the Director of the state's Tourism Board, as earlier quoted. This finding is also similar to the conclusion of Folorunso *et al.*, (2017), who posit that tourism products of cultural resources owes so much to proper management and for their acceptability and promotion. Equally, the Curator of Esie Museum, Mr. Mayowa quoted that *"that cultural resources of tourism potentials in the state needs to be properly harnessed to attract visitors' attentions."*

ii. **Inadequate Management and Systemic Challenges in CRM**

One of the primary barriers to sustainable tourism development in Kwara State is the lack of a systematic approach to CRM, which has resulted in neglect, poor maintenance, and deterioration of cultural resources. Studies have shown that effective CRM requires well-defined policies, proper documentation, and regular conservation efforts (Timothy & Nyaupane, 2009). However, findings suggest that several cultural sites in Kwara State suffer from weak management structures due to a lack of trained personnel and conservation strategies (Adebayo & Iweka, 2019). This was substantiated by Alfa Alsorowy, one of the custodians of Sheik Alimi Mosque. He explained that *the Sheik Alimi Mosque and Olofa's Palace, which have historical significance, are gradually deteriorating due to insufficient preservation measures*". Reports from previous research indicate that over 60% of cultural sites in Nigeria face maintenance issues due to inadequate CRM implementation (Bassey & Udo, 2020). Furthermore, poor documentation and limited digital archiving of heritage assets make it difficult to promote cultural sites effectively, reducing their visibility among potential visitors (Okonkwo, 2023).

iii. **Financial Constraints and Limited Conservation Efforts**

The findings indicate that financial constraints remain a significant challenge to effective CRM and sustainable tourism development in Kwara State. Insufficient funding affects conservation activities, infrastructure development, and promotional efforts, leading to the gradual decline of cultural resources (Kukoyi *et al.*, 2018; Muganda *et al.*, 2021). Many of the state's cultural attractions lack proper maintenance due to budgetary limitations, which have resulted in inadequate signage, poor visitor facilities, and the deterioration of artifacts. In the words of Alabede, the Director of Kwara State Tourism Board, *"Streamlined budgetary allocation from the ministry is curtailing tourism awareness in the state."* To substantiate this, according to a report by Tunde *et al.*, (2022), nearly 70% of Nigerian heritage sites lack consistent funding, which hampers effective site management. In Kwara State, government subventions for cultural heritage preservation remain low, while private sector investment in heritage tourism is minimal. This has led to over-reliance on entrance fees and occasional grants, which are insufficient for large-scale conservation projects (Akintunde *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, many local businesses and hospitality firms do not see the economic value of investing in cultural heritage tourism, further limiting financial resources for site preservation.

iv. **Weak Stakeholder Engagement and Poor Institutional Collaboration**

The study also found that low stakeholder engagement and weak collaboration among government agencies, local communities, and tourism stakeholders hinder inclusive tourism development (Bello & Olalekan, 2022; Balogun, 2023). Sustainable CRM requires active participation from multiple stakeholders, including government tourism boards, traditional leaders, private investors, and local communities (Sharpley & Telfer, 2015). However, findings suggest that in Kwara State, there is a lack of coordinated efforts among key actors, leading to inefficiencies in heritage site management. Mr. Salaudeen, a tourism officer at the KSTB, as quoted *"There is no official relationship between NCMM and the custodians of tourist attractions in the state"*. For example, the Ilorin Emirate Palace and Esie Museum, despite their historical importance, have not benefited from strong partnerships between the National Commission for Museums and Monuments (NCMM) and local tourism agencies (Okonkwo, 2023). Additionally, local communities, who are the custodians of cultural heritage, are often excluded from decision-making processes, reducing their sense of ownership and participation in conservation efforts (Mthembu & Chiweshe, 2023). This has led to weak policy enforcement and limited community-driven conservation initiatives, further exacerbating the problem of cultural resource degradation (Pisolkar 2024).

v. **Stagnation Phase of Cultural Attractions Based on TALC Model**

Analysis of Kwara State's cultural attractions using the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) model indicates that several heritage sites are in the stagnation phase, requiring strategic rejuvenation efforts to prevent further decline (Butler, 1980). The stagnation phase is

characterised by declining visitor numbers, outdated infrastructure, and loss of appeal due to inadequate investment and promotion (Rogerson & van der Merwe, 2016). The state tourism board provided estimated data in terms of number of visitors to some of the cultural resources' attractions under consideration. Mr Salaudeen quote that *"many students prefer to go to neighbouring states, such as Osun and Oyo for tourism activities because the tourist sites in Kwara state have been neglected"*. Mrs Jimoh, one the Potters at Dada Pottery added that *"the number of visitors has decreased over time and most of them do not buy the pots why they come, they just take pictures and ask questions"* This implies that tourists are not being entirely satisfied with their experience of Kwara State's cultural resources, thereby not making a repeat visit or discourage others about visiting the sites.

- vi. Findings suggest that attractions such as Sheik Alimi Mosque and Olofa's Palace in Offa have reached stagnation due to a combination of neglect, weak marketing strategies, and infrastructure decay (Bello & Olalekan, 2022). Additionally, tourism activities in these locations have not evolved to incorporate modern trends such as digital heritage experiences and interactive guided tours, which have been successfully implemented in other African cultural destinations (Hassan *et al.*, 2023). However, research has shown that destinations in the stagnation phase can undergo successful rejuvenation through strategic interventions, including improved marketing, infrastructure upgrades, and enhanced visitor engagement (Johnson & Williams, 2024). For instance, similar heritage sites in Kenya and South Africa have implemented digital tourism innovations, including virtual reality tours and online ticketing systems, to attract new visitor demographics and rejuvenate cultural tourism (Pisolkar, 2024). Applying such strategies in Kwara State could revitalise its heritage sites and extend their tourism life cycle.

Discussion of Findings

The findings highlight the urgent need for a structured CRM framework in Kwara State to address financial constraints, improve stakeholder collaboration, and enhance site management practices. Given that several cultural attractions are in the stagnation phase, strategic rejuvenation efforts, including infrastructure investment, community involvement, and digital heritage promotion, are essential to sustaining cultural tourism in the state. The application of the TALC model and the Tripod of Sustainability framework can help policymakers to develop targeted interventions that balance economic, social, and environmental considerations to ensure long-term sustainability. In the context of international best practice, Okonkwo (2023) documented integrated heritage management planning, which is adopted in the United Kingdom, evident in the heritage management plan of Stonehenge. This practice also encapsulates stakeholders' collaboration and community involvement, evident in the Waitangi Treaty Grounds in New Zealand. The Great Wall Conservation Program in China adopted heritage conservation and restoration techniques.

The findings suggest that Cultural Resource Management (CRM) practices in Kwara State insufficiently address the three pillars of sustainability, economic, environmental, and social. While there are concerted efforts to promote the economic benefits of cultural tourism, particularly through increased visitor spending and job creation in the hospitality sector, environmental conservation and social equity remain areas that require significant improvement. The current CRM strategies largely prioritise revenue generation from cultural sites such as Esie Museum, Olofa's Palace, and Ilorin Emirate Palace, with limited attention to preservation of the cultural heritage of the sites, mitigating environmental and physical degradation or ensuring equitable benefits for local communities. This aligns with McKercher's (2003) assertion that sustainable tourism must integrate environmental responsibility and social inclusivity alongside economic gains.

A critical gap identified in the study is the lack of comprehensive environmental management strategies within CRM frameworks. Many heritage sites suffer from inadequate waste management, deforestation, and uncontrolled urban expansion, which threaten the long-term sustainability of these attractions. For instance, the lack of structured conservation policies for heritage landmarks like Sheik Alimi Mosque and Sobi Hill has led to gradual deterioration,

impacting both their historical significance and their tourism potential. In tandem, Timothy & Nyaupane, (2009); Rogerson & van der Merwe (2016), emphasise the necessity of integrating green tourism practices, such as controlled visitor numbers, energy-efficient infrastructure, and strict heritage conservation policies, to ensure the longevity of cultural tourism resources.

In terms of social sustainability, community participation remains low, as many residents are not actively involved in decision-making processes regarding cultural resource management. This exclusionary approach often leads to conflicts between tourism stakeholders and indigenous communities, who feel marginalised despite being custodians of the cultural heritage. According to Bramwell & Lane (2011), sustainable tourism development should emphasise inclusive governance that empowers local communities and fosters their active engagement in planning and decision-making. In Kwara State, the absence of policies that integrate local artisans, historians, and cultural custodians into CRM structures limits the potential of heritage sites as avenues for community-driven tourism and economic empowerment.

To address these gaps, this study advocates for a revised approach to tourism development that aligns CRM with global sustainable practices, as highlighted above. This would involve a multi-stakeholder collaboration between government agencies, local communities, private investors, and non-governmental organisations to promote eco-friendly tourism initiatives, enforce heritage site conservation regulations, and enhance community participation in tourism planning. Additionally, leveraging digital innovations such as virtual heritage tours, smart tourism applications, and interactive museum experiences could further improve cultural heritage interpretation while minimising physical degradation (Okonkwo, 2023). This implies that integration of sustainability principles into CRM frameworks will allow Kwara State to maximise the long-term benefits of its rich cultural resources while safeguarding them for future generations.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demand a policy reformation in the aspect of CRM in Kwara State. One of the most applicable strategies is the Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) Model which has been employed in the United Kingdom, China, New Zealand and South Africa. This model creates a synergy between the Government, private sector and community with each having a distinct role to play. The government specifically provides regulatory frameworks, incentives, and funding support for cultural heritage preservation, and also facilitates land and infrastructure development at key cultural sites. While the private sector is encouraged to invest in tourism facilities, digital innovations, and marketing campaigns, thereby introducing corporate sponsorships and branding opportunities for heritage conservation projects. The community, on the other hand, must serve as local custodians and active participants in cultural tourism initiatives; they are expected to engage in heritage tourism entrepreneurship and guided tour services.

Digital innovation strategies for cultural site rejuvenation must be embraced to complement the PPP model by developing smart tourism applications offering immersive storytelling, interactive maps, and guided audio tours. The implementation of virtual heritage tours for global accessibility and cultural promotion will help to establish digital archiving systems, document and preserve Kwara's historical and cultural assets. This can also be achieved through integrated Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) experiences to enhance visitor engagement and learning. The aftermath of this strategy will result into the launching of cultural tourism festivals and events that attract both domestic and international tourists. The CRM stakeholders must partner with travel influencers, content creators, and media platforms to amplify Kwara's tourism appeal. A centralised tourism information portal can be developed through the Kwara State Tourism Board for a seamless visitor experience and trip planning.

In light of the above, recommendations for sustainable cultural tourism development will include but not be limited to, the following:

- i. Comprehensive Cultural Resource Management (CRM) Strategy, which can be achieved by establishing a state-level CRM framework that integrates systematic planning, conservation measures, and stakeholder collaboration.
- ii. Development of a CRM policy document outlining specific preservation, management, and sustainability strategies for cultural sites.

- iii. Integration of the TALC Model in tourism planning by assessing the life cycle stage of each cultural heritage site and implement targeted rejuvenation strategies this will encourage periodic audits of cultural sites to monitor visitor trends, conservation needs, and economic viability.
- iv. Strengthening Environmental and Social Sustainability through the promotion of eco-friendly infrastructure development at cultural sites, including waste management, green energy solutions, and sustainable visitor facilities.
- v. Implementation of community-based tourism models that ensure equitable revenue-sharing and active local participation in tourism decision-making.
- vi. Enhancement of heritage tourism marketing and digital innovation by redefining Kwara State's tourism branding to position it as a premier cultural tourism hub in Nigeria.
- vii. Leveraging digital tourism innovations such as virtual tours, digital archiving, and interactive heritage site applications to enhance accessibility and engagement.
- viii. Multi-stakeholder collaboration and investment strategies through the establishment of a multi-sectoral tourism board comprising government agencies, private investors, cultural experts, and local communities.
- ix. Strengthen partnerships with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and international heritage conservation bodies to attract funding and expertise, such as the case of Osun Osogbo Sacred Grove.

References

- Adebayo, H. & Iweka, O. (2019). Sustainable development and environmental conservation in Nigeria: The role of stakeholders. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 13(2), 145-156
- Tunde, A. M., Okunade, J. O., & Omojola, P. O. (2022). A review of cultural festivals and cultural tourism development in rural areas of Nigeria. *HATMAN Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 12(1), 87-96
- Pisolkar, Y. (2024). Cultural heritage management and sustainable development: Major themes and research trajectories. *Journal of Electrical Systems*, 20(6), 2417-2431
- Afolabi, O. & Ayodele, T. (2020). Exploring the potential of cultural heritage tourism in Kwara State, Nigeria. *West African Journal of Tourism and Hospitality*, 5(4), 78-94.
- Akintunde, R., Olatunji, S., & Okeke, I. (2022). Private sector investment in cultural tourism: Challenges and opportunities in Nigeria. *Journal of Tourism and Business Development*, 10(2), 55-73.
- Balogun, K. B. (2023). *Promotion Media and Tourism Development of Cultural Festivals in Oyo Town, Nigeria* (Faculty of Multidisciplinary Studies, University of Ibadan, Doctoral Thesis).
- Balogun, K. B. & Ajagunna, A. E. (2023). Exploring the Influence of Demographic Factors on Perceptions of Festival Tourism in Ilara-Mokin, Nigeria: A Social Exchange Analysis. *Journal of Tourismology*, 9(2), 169-179.
- Bassey, U. & Udo, E. (2020). Heritage site conservation and tourism development in Nigeria: A policy evaluation approach. *African Journal of Cultural Policy*, 6(1), 33-49.
- Bello, K. & Olalekan, S. (2022). Cultural heritage management and tourism sustainability: A study of Ilorin and Offa heritage sites in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Tourism and Sustainable Development Journal*, 8(2), 120-137.
- Bramwell, B. & Lane, B. (2011). Sustainable tourism: An evolving global approach. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(4-5), 411-424.
- Bramwell, B., & Lane, B. (2011). Critical research on the governance of tourism and sustainability. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(4), 401-410.
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Butler, R. W. (1980). The concept of a tourism area cycles of evolution: Implications for management of resources. *Canadian Geographer*, 24(1), 5-12.
- Folorunso, O. S., Bashiru, A. A., Festus, A. S. & Adebayo, H. M. (2024). Assessing the impact of rural tourism on entrepreneurial development. *Benin Journal of Religions and Society*, Vol 6 (2): 230-243 ISSN:2636-6622

- Hassan, A., Nwankwo, C., & Yusuf, O. (2023). Technology-driven heritage tourism: Enhancing visitor experience through digital platforms. *Journal of Tourism and Heritage Innovation*, 11(1), 145-163.
- Holden, A. (2016). *Environment and tourism* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Johnson, P. & Williams, D. (2024). Tourism area life cycle and destination rejuvenation strategies: Lessons from global case studies. *International Journal of Tourism Management*, 15(1), 33-50.
- Kukoyi, I. A., Aremu, D. A., Ololajulo, B. O., & Balogun, K. B. (2018). Reinvention of Ojude-Oba Festival for Tourism and its Impact on the Host Community. *Agidigbo: ABUAD Journal of the Humanities*, 6(1), 47-57.
- McKercher, B. (2003). Sustainable tourism development: A critique of the existing literature. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 11(3), 328-339.
- Mthembu, L. & Chiweshe, M. (2023). Community engagement and cultural heritage management in Africa: Challenges and policy recommendations. *Journal of Cultural and Social Research*, 14(3), 98-115.
- Muganda, M., Sirima, A., & Marwa, S. (2021). Financial sustainability in cultural tourism: A critical review of African heritage sites. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 23(4), 77-94.
- Okonkwo, J. (2023). The role of digital archiving in preserving African cultural heritage. *Journal of African Digital Studies*, 7(2), 60-78.
- Rogerson, C. M. & van der Merwe, C. (2016). Heritage tourism in South Africa: A geographical perspective. *Tourism Geographies*, 18(3), 274-296.
- Sharpley, R. & Telfer, D. J. (2015). *Tourism and development: Concepts and issues* (2nd ed.). Channel View Publications.
- Smith, L. (2006). *Uses of heritage*. Routledge.
- Timothy, D. J. & Nyaupane, G. P. (2009). *Cultural heritage and tourism in the developing world: A regional perspective*. Routledge.
- Timothy, D. J. (2011). *Cultural heritage and tourism: An introduction*. Channel View Publications.
- United Nations World Tourism Organisation (2024). UNWTO special bulletin on World Tourism Day celebration in Georgia on Tourism and Peace. www.unwto.org Madrid, Spain